

CP4: MtrunA17_Chr1g0149991

CP9: MtrunA17_Chr1g0158341

CP12: MtrunA17_Chr1g0178361

CP37: MtrunA17_Ch2g0299561

CP44: MtrunA17_Chr2g0326801

CP61: MtrunA17_Chr3g0137391

CP62: MtrunA17_Chr3g0141901

-1 (2a2→1a1)

CP94: MtrunA17_Chr5g0444231

CP98: MtrunA17_Chr6g0457461

-1 (1r→3a)

+1 (3r→1a)

-1 (1r→3a)

-1 (2a→1r)

-2 (1a1→2a2)

+1 (1r→2a)

-2 (3r→1a)

+1 (3r→1a)

+2 (2a1→1a2)

+2 (2a1→1a2)

Supplementary Dataset S7 Part 4. A graphical summary on folding predictions for 90 MS-supported chimeric peptide models (CPs) that contain alpha-helices and no beta-sheets. For each CP, one image is displayed: the predicted folding structure (top) along with heat maps of five predictions (bottom). The rest of the legend is the same as for Supplementary Dataset S7 Part 1.